

PREPARATION AND THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MORTAR CONTAINING OCTADECANE/xGNP SSPCM

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1. Introduction

Thermal energy storage (TES) technologies have been received as a purpose of efficient energy usage. There are two types of TES, sensible storage and latent storage. Particularly, TES system using phase change materials (PCM) which is very beneficial because of their large thermal storage ability in relatively small volumes has been widely utilized in waste heat applications, solar and ground heat power plants, buildings in the world [1,2]. PCMs have high latent heat of fusion during a phase change. PCMs undergo charging the heat with melting and discharging the heat with solidification as it stays in hot and cold environment [3].

Despite its huge potential, they have a couple of problems: leakage during the solid-liquid phase change, lower thermal conductivity of PCMs, and limited cycles of melting and solidification. Some investigators have studied the possibility of a container that can prevent the leaking of liquid PCMs to solve these problems. The alternative methods of the container that can prevent the leakage of liquid PCMs are using Microencapsulated PCM (MPCM) and Shape-Stabilized PCM (SSPCM) techniques. Zhang and Niu [4] researched the experimental investigation of super-cooling on MPCM slurry for thermal storage capacities. MPCM slurry has been made by microencapsulating phase change material with a thin film as shell and dispersing the MPCM into an aqueous solution as a carrier fluid. Hexadecane was the core material that has melting temperature is 18 °C, and latent heat is 234 J/g, and amino plastics as shell material. Sari et al. [5] introduced the microencapsulated octacosane as PCM for thermal energy storage. This study deals with preparation and characterization of polymethylmethacrylate microcapsules covering n-octacosane as phase change material. The melting and freezing temperatures and the latent heats of the microencapsulated octacosane as PCM were measured as 50.6 ~ 53.2 °C, 86.4 ~ 88.5 J/g. Jeong et al. [6] proposed SSPCM that is consisted of an

organic PCM, hexadecane, octadecane and paraffin wax, and diatomite using vacuum impregnation method. The SSPCM showed have latent heat capacities of 254.7 J/g, 247.6 J/g and 144.6 J/g, and melting points of 20.8 °C, 30.4 °C, and 57.1 °C respectively. Karaman et al. [7] concluded thermal energy storage properties of polyethylene glycol/diatomite composite as a novel form-stable composite PCM. The composite PCM was prepared by incorporating PEG in the pores of diatomite.

Even the methods to solve the leakage problem of PCM have been suggested by many researchers, they showed still the low thermal conductivity that have a strong effect on the heat storage efficiency of materials. In other word, there is no use in utilizing without swift heat transfer when they are demanded no matter what PCMs have a large capacity of heat storage. These weaknesses reduce the rate of heat storage and off during the melting and solidification cycles and limit to their broad applications idea. A lot of ways to enhance the thermal conductivity of PCM have been attempted. The methods of diffusing metallic or nonmetallic particles with high thermal conductivity into PCMs [8–11], casing finned tubes with different arrangements in a storage unit [12–14], and impregnating PCM into high thermal conductivity material such as carbon materials with porous structure [15–18] have been researched.

This research prepared SSPCM to solve the leakage problem keeping their efficient thermal storage quantity and to improve the thermal conductivity. Octadecane was employed as a heat storage media which has a suitable temperature range of comfortable indoor environment. Exfoliated graphite nanoplate (xGnP), which is porous and a nano-sized carbon material, was used to improve thermal conductivity and heat storage efficiency. The microstructure and thermal properties of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) and thermo gravimetric

analysis (TGA). Moreover, mortars containing different contents of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM were prepared to determine its thermal characteristics as building construction application and to verify the thermal performance to save building energy.

2. Octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

2.1 Material

Octadecane, $C_{18}H_{38}$, is made of alkane series and belongs to organic PCM. Table 1 shows properties of octadecane.

Table 1. Properties of octadecane [19]

Melting temperature ($^{\circ}C$)	28.0
Heat storage capacity (J/g)	256.5
Specific heat capacity (J/g·K)	92.0
Thermal conductivity (W/m·K)	0.26
Density (kg/m^3) at $25^{\circ}C$	777.0

xGnP is a graphitic carbon-based material. The graphite was obtained from Asbury Graphite Mills, Inc., NJ, USA, by applying a cost- and time-effective exfoliation process initially proposed by the Drzal group [20]. xGnP which combine the layered structure and low price of nanoclays with the superior mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of carbon nanotubes, is very cost effective and can simultaneously provide multitude of physical and chemical property enhancements [21-24]. Table 1 contains the physical properties of xGnP.

Table 2. Properties of xGnP

Surface area (m^2/g)	20.41
Bulk density (g/cm^3)	0.0053-0.010
Pore volume (cm^3/g)	0.081
Thermal conductivity (W/m·K)	2-300
Specific heat capacity (J/kg·K)	710

2.2 Preparation of Octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

Octadecane/xGnP SSPCM was prepared by impregnation method in a vacuum. The image of the vacuum impregnation system is shown in Fig. 1. xGnP was placed inside a filtering flask, which was connected to a water trap apparatus to evacuate air from its porous surface. Then, the valve between the flask and a container with octadecane in liquid state PCM was opened to permit flow into the flask to cover the xGnP sample. The vacuum process was continued for 60 min, and then air was allowed to enter the flask again to force the liquid PCM to penetrate into the pore space of xGnP. Octadecane/xGnP composite in a colloidal state was filtered by a $1\ \mu m$ glass fiber filter paper until granular sample appeared, which was dried in a vacuum drier at $80^{\circ}C$ for 24 hours. The appearance of xGnP and octadecane/xGnP SSCM in Fig. 2 was taken a picture at $20^{\circ}C$ in the lab. As shown it, xGnP is the type of black powder, and prepared octadecane/xGnP SSCM is the type of black granule. New composite that has the melting point $28^{\circ}C$ of octadecane could existed on the solid state at $20^{\circ}C$.

Fig. 1. Vacuum equipment to prepare SSPCM.

Fig. 2. (a) xGnP and (b) octadecane/xGnP SSPCM.

2.3 Characterization techniques

Microstructure of samples was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at room temperature. SEM with an accelerating voltage of 12 kV and a working distance of 12 mm was used to collect SEM images.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR: 300E Jasco) was also utilized to monitor the change of chemical groups upon curing. The samples were analyzed over the range of $500 - 4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a spectrum resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . All spectra were averaged over 32 scans. This analysis of xGnP, octadecane, the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM was performed at a point-to-point contact with a pressure device [25].

Thermal conductivities of the pure octadecane and the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM were measured by TCi thermal conductivity analyzer with the size of 20 mm-diameter and 10 mm thickness at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The

TCi can measure thermal conductivity of a small specimen by using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) method. Contrary to other devices, TCi can measure the thermal conductivity of materials in solid, liquid, powder, or mixed states. In addition, it can measure the thermal conductivity using only one side [26].

Thermal properties such as the melting temperature and latent heat capacity of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM using a differential scanning calorimetry (DSC: Q 1000). DSC measurements were performed at a $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ heating and cooling rate and temperature ranges of 0 to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 80 to $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The melting temperature was measured by drawing a line at the point of maximum slope of the leading edge of the peak and extrapolating to the base line. The latent heat of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM was determined by numerical integration of the area under the peaks that represent the solid–solid and solid–liquid phase transitions.

Thermo gravimetric analysis measurements of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM were carried out using a thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA: TA Instruments, TGA Q5000) on approximately $2 - 4 \text{ mg}$ samples over the temperature range $25 - 600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under a nitrogen flow of $20 \text{ ml}/\text{min}$. TGA was measured with the composites placed in high quality nitrogen, 99.5% nitrogen, 0.5% oxygen content, atmosphere to prevent unwanted oxidation [27].

2.4 Properties of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

Scanning electron microscopy observations were performed for the xGnP and octadecane/xGnP SSPCM as shown in Fig. 3. Porous xGnP is shown in Fig. 3(a). It was found that the xGnP has a good structure for incorporating liquefied materials such as PCM. Fig. 3(b) can be seen that octadecane is incorporated into the pores of the xGnP evenly. The octadecane almost fully filled the diatomite pores. As a result of SEM analysis, it can be confirmed that octadecane incorporated well into the structure of xGnP and expect the characteristic of heat storage properties of the PCMs to display in the composites.

Fig. 3. SEM images of (a) xGnP and (b) octadecane/xGnP SSPCM.

FTIR absorption spectra of the xGnP, octadecane and the octadecane/xGnP composites are shown in Fig. 4. The octadecane has molecular formulae of $C_{18}H_{38}$ and is composed of $-CH_2$ bonding and $-CH_3$ bonding. These FTIR absorption spectra were found with absorption peaks of 2910 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch), 1470 cm^{-1} (C-H Bending) and 717 cm^{-1} (C=O) caused by stretching vibration of functional groups of $-CH_2$ and $-CH_3$. We confirmed that these bondings were not broken or changed during the incorporating process as seen in the octadecane/xGnP composite peaks. The pure xGnP shows main absorption bands at 2350 cm^{-1} ($O=C=O$). The FTIR spectrum of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM has new absorption peaks at 2918 cm^{-1} , 2350 cm^{-1} , 1470 cm^{-1} and 717 cm^{-1} . In this experiment, it was found that the FTIR adsorption spectra of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM did not change from their chemical characteristics. This explains that there is no chemical interaction between octadecane and xGnP. The octadecane molecules were retained

easily in the pores of xGnP by these physical interactions such as capillary and surface tension forces, which led to no leakage of the melted PCM. Consequently, it was determined that the heat storage characteristics of octadecane could integrate into the structure of xGnP due to its physical bonding, without a change in its chemical properties.

Fig. 4. FTIR absorption spectra of xGnP, octadecane, and octadecane/xGnP SSPCM.

The study of the effects of xGnP on the octadecane to enhance thermal transition ability was studied by the thermal conductivity test using TCi. As presented in Table 3, the thermal conductivity of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM increased by 5.2 times comparing to the pure octadecane at $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. It is clearly indicated that the addition of xGnP into the PCM results in increase thermal transition ability for heat absorption and release. Moreover, the change in appearance color of the new composite was found as black by xGnP from white which is the original color of octadecane as shown in Fig 5.

Table 3. Thermal conductivity of pure octadecane and octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

	Pure Octadecane	Octadecane/xGnP SSPCM
Thermal conductivity	0.260 W/m·K	1.363 W/m·K

Fig. 5. (a) Pure octadecane and (b) octadecane/xGnP SSPCM.

DSC analysis was carried out to confirm thermal properties of the samples. Fig. 6 shows the specific heat of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM. It is sharply increased during the transition temperature range of the SSPCM from solid to liquid state, and gets the peak point at the liquid state in a whole. The specific heat of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM is 14.1 J/g·K at 31.3 °C. These DSC peaks of heating and cooling show the latent heat storage of octadecane. The heating and freezing curves from the DSC measurement of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM are presented in Fig. 7. The latent heats are obtained by numerical integration of the total area under the peaks of the solid–liquid transition curves of the PCMs in the composite. It can be seen that the latent heats of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM approach to 110.9 J/g for heating and 104.5 J/g for cooling which is about a half of heat storage performance of the pure octadecane. As shown Fig. 7, the phase transition of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM took a place the melting temperature range between 22 °C to 33 °C with 110.9 J/g of thermal storage capacity and the freezing temperature range 26 °C to 19 °C with 104.5 J/g of thermal releasing capacity. The quantity variation of thermal storage capacity and thermal

releasing capacity was 1.6J/g which indicates that the prepared SSPCM played a stable heat storage performance. This high latent heat storage of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM has an important potential for heating and cooling applications in buildings.

Fig. 6. Specific heat of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM.

Fig. 7. Heating & cooling behaviors of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

TGA test was performed ranging from 20 °C to 600 °C to determine the percentage of impregnation of the SSPCM. As a result of TGA test in Fig. 8, decomposition of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM started from 100 °C and ended at 205 °C. xGnP is a carbon-based material that has thermal resistance properties so that it did not decompose on the tested temperature range. Namely, all of the decomposed material was the octadecane, and the percentage of impregnated octadecane was 55.9%. It shows that impregnation of PCM into the xGnP negatively affects the thermal durability of PCM. However, in the case of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM, the xGnP

still remained in the samples although PCM was fully oxidized. Therefore, it shows that the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM has a higher thermal durability compared to the pure octadecane.

Fig. 8. TGA curve of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM.

3. Heat storage mortar containing octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

3.1 Preparation of mortar containing octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

Different contents of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM were mixed with the mortar as percentages of cement mass content, 10, 20, and 30 wt.%. Water : cement ratio was 1 : 2, and the sand : cement ratio was 1 : 2. After casting and surface finishing samples were completed, the mortar containing octadecane/xGnP SSPCM were stored in water containers at 20 °C for 28 curing days.

3.2 Thermal characterization techniques

3.2.1 Thermal conductivity

All types of samples for thermal conductivity measurement were prepared by TCi thermal conductivity analyzer with the size of 100 mm × 100 mm × 20 mm (*l* × *w* × *t*). The method is not applicable when a phase change occurs in the material, as might be the case with the PCM containing mixes. To overcome the problem, the samples have been heated to 40 °C which is the temperature that the octadecane is in the liquid state completely.

3.2.2 Heating/cooling behavior of SSPCM

To measure the influence of SSPCM contents on the peak temperature during hydration, an experimental setup has been constructed as presented in Fig. 9. The sample-shaped of this heating/cooling behavior test measures 300 mm × 300 mm × 20 mm (*l* × *w* × *t*). The four samples were individually separated by the fixed wall. The wall was constructed with the layer of plywood panel, 15 mm thick with a thermal conductivity of 0.125 W/m·K, and rock wool, 100 mm thick with 0.037 W/m·K, formed a semi-adiabatic environment. Heat source was 250 W of far-infrared radiation lamp to imitate the solar energy performance. The heat source provided the heat for the samples with keeping the distance of 1 m. Each of heating and cooling time kept for 6 hours which was 12 hours to finish this test. Thermocouples (type T) were placed to measure the temperature during the heating and cooling time on the front and back side of samples. Data acquisition took place by using data logger, LOGGER GL800 by Graphtec, in combination with a personal computer to store the data.

Fig.9. Heating/cooling behavior test setup

3.3 Results and discussion

The study of the effects of PCM on the thermal properties of mortar includes measurements of thermal conductivity and heating/cooling behavior.

Thermal conductivity measurements are presented in Fig. 10. It is indicated that addition of the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM into the mass of the mortar results in increase in thermal conductivity. This can be explained by the higher thermal conductivity of a red octadecane/xGnP SSPCM,

1.363 W/m·K, than the pure octadecane, 0.260 W/m·K.

Fig. 10. Thermal conductivity of mortar containing octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

An appropriate method of evaluating the effect of octadecane/xGnP SSPCM on thermal efficiency of structural elements is the comparison at the indoor surface of a wall with different amounts of the SSPCM. Evaluation of thermal performance of building materials used for building envelopes was performed by measuring the decrement temperature and time lag. In the current work, the above described thermal analysis device was used to simulate indoor and outdoor temperatures and the corresponding temperature profiles were imposed on the front and back sides of the sample. The outdoor temperature was assumed to have a range from 23 °C to 28 °C for 8 hours, while the indoor temperature was set stable at a level of 20 °C. Temperatures on both surfaces of the same samples as the ones are recorded. Integration of the measured temperature on the inner side of the sample introduced a measure of the total heat lag for the indoor environment. The temperature measurements during the heating time demonstrate an up to 5.9 °C of maximum variation at early 230 min (at $x_{230\text{min}}$ in Fig. 11) and 104 min of time lag effect until the inner side of sample reached at 27 °C (at $y_{27^\circ\text{C}}$ in Fig. 11) when the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM-free mortar and the 30% SSPCM contents were compared. Moreover, the temperature measurements during cooling time determined an up to 2.3 °C of maximum temperature variation after the cooling start point at 190 min (at $x_{670\text{min}}$ in Fig. 10) and 58 min of time lag effect until the inner side of sample peaked at 27 °C (at $y_{27^\circ\text{C}}$ in Fig. 11). As analyzed

above, the time lag effect was found through the phase change temperature of the octadecane, 22 to 33 °C, during heating and cooling. After finishing the capacity of heat storage of the PCM, the temperature variations were getting decreased because of the thermal conductivity of the mortar containing the octadecane/xGnP SSPCM that was increased thermal conductivity as more the SSPCM contents was mixed. Therefore, it can be clearly demonstrated that prepared SSPCM brought about the very effective time lag performance in the range of thermal comfort indoor temperature and quick releasing heat.

Fig. 11. Heating/cooling behavior of mortars containing octadecane/xGnP SSPCM

4. Conclusion

This research developed a product which would realize important building energy savings with the improvement of the heat storage mortar using innovative type of phase change materials on thermal property. The work here presented is the preparation of thermally developed new SSPCM and introducing the thermal storage mortar as a building material.

Octadecane/xGnP SSPCM was developed to prevent the leakage with retaining efficient thermal storage capacity. Octadecane that have melting temperature 28 °C was used as the PCM. xGnP that is porous and nano-sized carbon material was good container for PCM due to its many porous, high surface area, and high thermal conductivity. According to TGA data, octadecane impregnated into xGnP as much 55.9 % of prepared SSPCM composite. The octadecane/xGnP SSPCM had the melting temperature range 22 °C to 33 °C with 110.9

J/g of thermal storage capacity, and a freezing temperature range 26 °C to 19 °C with 104.5 J/g of thermal releasing capacity. In addition, the prepared SSPCM was combined with a finishing mortar to enhance the thermal storage ability and to carry out time-lag effect from the harsh ambient air as a purpose of saving energy in buildings. The thermal properties of mortar mixing with the octadecan/xGnP SSPCM were identified to make it use real application for finishing material in buildings. As a result of the property tests, the tested mortar showed a good time-lag effect during heating time and reservation of temperature during the cooling, which allow building to reduce the peak temperature, to have smoother temperature flow, and to create comfortable thermal indoor environment. The utilization of new composite SSPCM amended the thermal energy storage rate of the LTES system considerably.

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